

Impact of Reforms on Operational Performance of Selected Public Sector Banks

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ABSTRACT- People's need for a safe place to deposit money led to the development of commercial banking. It didn't require a lot of investment for the individuals who held others' overflow cash to understand that their business could be made productive assuming they loan out again what was gotten by them, given that it was returned when it was required. The banking business is comprised of borrowing and lending, which are the bank's two primary functions. The modern banker performs numerous other duties in addition to these two fundamental ones. The following are the roles that commercial banks play namely Accepting Deposits, Advancing Loans, and Other Services.

KEYWORDS- Public Sector Banks, Accepting Deposits, Advancing Loans, Banking Business.

I. INTRODUCTION

A cash credit arrangement allows a customer to borrow money up to a certain amount against a pledge, hypothecation, or personal guarantee from the borrowers. This is the most widely recognized method of acquiring by enormous business and modern houses in India on account of the benefit that the borrower can pull out the sum as he expects at various times as opposed to getting the entire sum at one time. Additionally, they may deposit any surplus funds he may currently have in the bank. The customer is required to pay interest on at least half or quarter of the cash credit granted to him, even if he does not use that amount. Bankers cash credit agreements typically include a half or quarter interest clause. Cash credit interest rates range from 12.5 to 16.25 percent. A current account holder can get an overdraft

from a commercial bank, which allows him to take out more money than there is in the account up to a certain limit. Overdraft is allowable just on current records, typically against guarantee protections & pay interest on the sum really utilized by him. Limiting of bills is one more well-known type of advances endorsed by the financier [1, 3]. Alongside the over two center elements of Tolerating Stores and Authorizing of Advances, business banks likewise attempt such countless exercises, for example, assortment and installment of checks, bills and promissory notes, execution of standing requests, settlement of assets, issue of charge and Visas and different exercises. Additionally, the following two parameters can be used to explain the bank's operations.

- Branch expansion
- ATM centers established

II. ANALYSIS OF DEPOSIT MOBILIZATION

Finance is the backbone of any business. Banks prepare their money with regards to stores. The significance of banks as significant organizations for reserve funds preparation emerges, from their capacity to offer different segments of the general public, a great many saving instruments, joining various characteristics like liquidity adaptability and yield. There has been an extraordinary development of bank stores comparable to public pay and gross family investment funds during the most recent 50 years. The deposit mobilization patterns of State Bank of Hyderabad and Andhra Banks are revealed in the following analysis [2, 4].

Table 1: Deposit Mobilization of State Bank of Hyderabad during 2010-2022 (Rs. In Crores)

Deposit	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2020	2021	2022
Total	10614	12527	14841	17402	20568	24257	28929	34024	41502	50108
Fixed	6386	7781	9385	11377	13652	15916	19490	22341	28479	34774
Percentage in Total	60.16	62.11	63.23	65.38	66.37	65.61	67.37	65.66	68.62	69.40
Savings	2048	2405	2784	3194	3939	4757	5435	6855	7940	9409
Percentage in Total	19.29	19.20	18.76	18.35	19.15	19.61	18.79	20.15	19.13	18.78
Current	2180	2341	2672	2831	2977	3584	4004	4828	5083	5925
Percentage in Total	20.55	18.69	18.01	16.27	14.47	14.78	13.84	14.19	12.25	11.82

(Source: The annual reports of State Bank of Hyderabad)

Table 2: Growth in Deposits Mobilized by the State Bank of Hyderabad (In percentage)

Year	Total Deposits	Demand Deposits	Saving Deposits	Time Deposits
2013	---	---	---	---
2014	18.02	7.39	17.49	21.83
2015	18.47	14.14	15.76	20.62
2016	17.26	5.91	14.73	21.24
2017	18.37	5.19	23.32	20.26
2018	17.76	20.39	20.74	16.33
2019	19.26	11.72	14.28	22.46
2020	17.61	20.58	26.13	14.62
2021	21.98	5.28	15.81	27.48
2022	20.74	16.55	18.52	22.10

(Source: The annual reports of State Bank of Hyderabad)

III. DEPOSIT MOBILIZATION OF ANDHRA BANK

Store Assembly of Andhra Bank during 2013-2022 has been made sense of in Table –2. In 2013, Andhra Bank had a total of Rs. 10438 crores which have been expanded to Rs. 4,49,696 crores The share of fixed deposits in total deposits

has increased from Rs.7262 crores in 2013 to Rs.32832 crores in 2022, but it has decreased from 69.57 percent in 2013 to 66.43 percent in 2022[5,6].

Table 3: Growth in Deposits Mobilized by Andhra Bank during 2013-2022 (In percentage)

Year	Total Deposits	Demand Deposits	Saving Deposits	Time Deposits
2013	---	---	---	---
2014	38.12	71.76	22.18	38.82
2015	26.87	17.46	16.99	36.50
2016	1.09	7.31	18.92	-3.68
2017	13.90	15.05	25.63	10.39
2018	8.92	38.19	31.59	-1.77
2019	20.08	15.33	16.57	22.37
2020	23.13	20.56	24.76	22.82
2021	22.21	18.71	15.37	25.62
2022	19.24	20.43	14.39	20.99

(Source: The annual reports of Andhra Bank)

The investment funds store of Andhra Bank were Rs. 2259 crores with a level of 21.64 to add up to stores in 2013 and have expanded to Rs.12184 crores with a level of 24.65 in 2022. In 2022, there were Rs. 4409 crores in current deposits, up from Rs. \$917 million in 2013. The portion of current stores in the all-out stores 8.79 percent in 2013 has become 8.92 percent in 2022[7]. The expansion of both the total deposits and their components is detailed in Table 4.4. The all out stores development rate toward the start of the review was 38.12 percent, which has diminished to 19.24 percent in 2022. Beginning in 2005, the percentage of current deposits

increased to 71.76 percent, falling to 20.43 percent in 2022. Andhra Bank's saving deposits increased by 14.39 percent in 2022 from 22.16 percent in 2005. Also, fixed deposit growth has slowed down, from 38.62 percent in 2005 to 20.99 percent in 2022. By this investigation we presume that how much absolute stores and its parts were expanded year-to-year whereas the development pace of which has been diminished [8, 9].

IV. COMPARATIVE STUDY ON DEPOSIT MOBILIZATION

Table 4: Growth in Deposit Mobilization-A Comparative Study of State Bank of- Hyderabad with Andhra Bank

Bank Name	Year	Total Deposits	Demand Deposits	Savings Deposits	Time Deposits
S B H	2013	10614	2180	2048	6386
ANDHRA BANK	2014	10438	917	2259	7262
S B H	2015	12527	2341	2405	7781
ANDHRA BANK	2016	14417	1575	2760	10081
S B H	2017	14841	2672	2784	9385
ANDHRA BANK	2018	18291	1300	3229	13761
S B H	2019	17402	2831	3194	11377
ANDHRA BANK	2020	18490	1395	3840	13255
S B H	2021	20568	2977	3939	13652
ANDHRA BANK		21061	1605	4824	14632
S B H	2013	24257	3584	4757	15916
ANDHRA BANK	2014	22940	2218	6348	14373
S B H	2015	28929	4004	5435	19490
ANDHRA BANK	2016	27547	2558	7400	17588
S B H	2017	34024	4828	6855	22341
ANDHRA BANK	2018	33919	3084	9232	21602
S B H	2019	41502	5083	7940	28479
ANDHRA BANK	2020	41451	3661	3661	27137
S B H	2021	50108	5925	9409	34774
ANDHRA BANK	2022	49426	4409	12184	32832

(Source: The annual reports of respective banks)

V. ANALYSIS OF LOANS DISBURSED

The State Bank of Hyderabad's total approved advances as well as their percentage growth rate from 2013 to 2022 are

shown in Table 6. The all out advances of State Bank of Hyderabad in 1999 were Rs.5331 crores and have been expanded to Rs.35848 crores. The development rate toward the start of the concentrate in 1999 was 15.16 percent and

comes to 27.53 percent in 2022. In 2021, the growth rate reached its highest point, 34.73 percent [10].

Table 5: Total Advances Sanctioned by State Bank of Hyderabad

Year	Total Advances (Rs. In Crores)	Growth (%)
2013	5331	15.16
2014	6087	14.17
2015	7091	16.49
2016	8422	18.77
2017	9662	14.72
2018	11813	22.26
2019	15599	32.05
2020	20863	33.74
2021	28109	34.73
2022	35848	27.53

(Source: The annual reports of State Bank of Hyderabad)

The advances that the State Bank of Hyderabad granted to the priority sector from 2013 to 2022 are depicted in Table 6. The advances endorsed to need area were Rs.1594 crores with a level of 29.90 to add up to propels and have been expanded to Rs.11752 crores which are 32.78 rate to add up to progresses. By this we can reason that the advances endorsed to need area have been expanded more than the expansion in complete advances by State Bank of

Hyderabad. The year-by-year development pace of advances to need area has not been a steady one, toward the start of the concentrate in the year 2005 it was 36.04 percent which promptly diminished to 13.57 percent in the year 2013 which later following 3 years in the year it has accomplished the most elevated development pace of study period 48.45 percent lastly in the year 2022 it is 7.24 percent [11, 12].

Table 6: Advances to Priority Sector by State Bank of Hyderabad (Rs. In crores)

Year	Total Advances	Advances Priority Sector	% in total	Growth (%)
2013	5331	1594	29.90	0.00
2014	6087	2168	35.63	36.04
2015	7091	2463	34.74	13.57
2016	8422	2898	34.41	17.66
2017	9662	3143	32.54	8.47
2018	11813	4667	39.51	48.45
2019	15599	6190	39.69	32.65
2020	20863	8695	41.68	40.46
2021	28109	10958	38.99	26.02
2022	35848	11752	32.78	7.24

(Source: The annual reports of State Bank of Hyderabad).

Table 7: Total Advances Sanctioned by Andhra Bank

Year	Total Advances (Rs. in Crores)	Growth (%)
2013	4524	37.25
2014	5573	69.09
2015	7423	33.18
2016	9677	30.37
2017	11512	18.96
2018	12885	11.92
2019	17516	35.94
2020	22100	26.17
2021	27889	26.19
2022	34238	22.77

(Source: The annual reports of Andhra Bank)

Table 8: Chart of Advances to Priority Sector by Andhra Bank

Year	Total Advances	Advances Priority Sector	% in total	Growth (%)
2013	4524	1874	40.97	41.96
2014	5573	2135	38.32	61.74
2015	7423	2652	35.73	24.18
2016	9677	3296	34.05	24.26
2017	11512	4594	39.90	39.38
2018	12885	4791	37.18	4.308
2019	17516	6907	39.43	44.15
2020	22100	8235	37.26	19.21
2021	27889	10454	37.48	26.95
2022	34238	12660	36.97	21.09

(Source: The annual reports of Andhra Bank)

VI. COMPARATIVE STUDY ON THE GROWTH IN TOTAL ADVANCES SANCTIONED TO THE PRIORITY SECTOR

A comparison of State Bank of Hyderabad and Andhra Bank's total advances and one of their most important component advances to the property sector is shown in Table 7. In 2013, State Bank of Hyderabad advanced Rs. 5331 crores, while Andhra Bank advanced Rs. 4524 crores. State Bank of Hyderabad's and Andhra Bank's total advances increased to Rs. 35848 crores and Rs. 34238 respectively by

the end of 2022. Around here toward the start of the concentrate as well as at end of the review time frame State Bank of Hyderabad has been overwhelming Andhra Bank with respect to add up to progresses authorized. However, the total advances granted by Andhra Bank exceeded those granted by State Bank of Hyderabad between 2013 and 2022[13, 14].

Table 9: A Comparative Study of State Bank of Hyderabad with AndhraBank (Rs. inCrores)

Year	Total advances of SBH	Growth (%)	Advances to Priority Sector SBH (Rs. In Crores)	Growth (%)	Total Advances of AB (Rs. In Crores)	Growth (%)	Advances to Priority Sector by AB (Rs. In Crores)	Growth (%)
2013	5331	---	1594	----	4524	----	1874	----
2014	6087	14.18	2168	36.01	5573	23.19	2135	13.93
2015	7091	16.49	2463	13.61	7423	33.20	2652	24.22
2016	8422	18.77	2898	17.66	9677	30.37	3296	24.28
2017	9662	14.72	3143	8.45	11512	18.96	4594	39.38
2018	11813	22.26	4667	48.49	12885	11.93	4791	4.29
2019	15599	32.05	6190	32.63	17516	35.94	6907	44.17
2020	20863	33.75	8695	40.47	22100	26.17	8235	19.23
2021	28109	34.73	10958	26.03	27889	26.19	10454	26.95
2022	35848	27.53	11752	7.25	34238	22.77	12660	21.10

(Source: The annual reports of respective banks)

A. Branch Expansion of State Bank of Hyderabad

Table - 8 shows the branch development of State Bank of Hyderabad. The quantity of Branches in 1969 were just 182, which have become 874 toward the finish of Walk, 2000 which have additionally expanded to 1096 up to the furthest limit of Walk, 2022. The Development record uncovers that, over a time of very nearly forty years the State Bank of Hyderabad has expanded its branch network multiple times (i.e.602.19%). It is likewise seen that there is a consistent expansion in branch organization [15].

B. Branch expansion of Andhra Bank

The expansion of Andhra Bank's branch network is depicted in Table 9. The Andhra Bank quickly expanded its branch network toward the actual starting that we can see by its development list. From 1969 to 1980 practically in multi decade it has expanded its branch network 6.5 times (for example 669.42%). It has grown to 1016 branches in 2000, up from 931 in 1980, over the course of twenty years. Additionally, Andhra Bank will have 1366 branches by the end of 2022. From 1969 to 2022, it has experienced a growth of 1028.93 percent over almost four decades [3, 16].

C. Deposit / Credit Per Branch Analysis

Table 10: Deposit per Office of State Bank of Hyderabad during 2013 -2022.

Year	Deposit per Branch (Rs. In Crores)	Growth (%)
2013	10.66	
2014	12.23	14.80
2015	14.37	17.44
2016	16.60	15.58
2017	19.64	18.25
2018	23.06	17.43
2019	27.32	18.47
2020	32.28	18.17
2021	38.75	20.04
2022	45.72	17.98

(Source: The annual reports of State Bank of Hyderabad)

D. Deposit per Branch Office of Andhra Bank-

From 2013 to 2022, Andhra Bank's deposit per branch is shown in Table -9. In 2013, the bank had a deposit per office of Rs.10.63 crore, which would rise to Rs.36.18 crore in 2022. Every year, with the exception of 2007, when the bank's deposit per office decreased from Rs.17.93 crores in 2013 to Rs.17.30 crores in 2007. The bank's growth rate in terms of deposit per office is also shown in the table. In 2005, the growth rate was 33.50 percent, and it will remain the same in 2022 at 12.52 percent.

E. Credit per Branch Office of the State Bank of Hyderabad

The State Bank of Hyderabad's credit per office is shown in Table 9. The bank's credit per office was Rs.0.54 crore in 2013, but that number will rise to Rs.3.27 crore in 2022. It likewise shows that the credit per office of the bank has been consistently expanding. The table additionally shows development pace of the credit per office of the bank. The growth rate was 11.07 percent at the beginning of the study period in 2013, and it was 23.30 percent at the end of the study period in 2022. Additionally, the growth rate has

slowed to 23.30 percent in 2022, down from 34.01 percent in 2022[6, 7].

F. Credit per Branch Office of the Andhra Bank

The Table - 9 shows credit per office of the Andhra Bank during 2013-2022. Credit per office of the bank in 2013 was Rs.0.46 crores expanded to Rs.2.51 crores in 2022. It likewise shows that the credit per office of the bank has been consistently expanding. The bank's credit growth rate per office is also shown in the table. The development rate toward the start of the review time frame in 2005 was 19.08 percent, toward the finish of the review time frame in 2022 set apart as 15.85 percent. The most elevated development rate has set apart as 32.66 in the year 2013 and most minimal in the year 2009 as 9.14 percent [11].

G. ATM Centers Established

The Popular electronic delivery channels are the followings:

- ATMs
- Smart Cards
- Tele Banking
- Internet Banking

Among the abovementioned, the most regularly utilized framework by greater part of individuals is ATM the full type of ATM is programmed Teller machine and individuals by and large term it as All Time Cash or Any Time Cash. An automated teller machine (ATM) is a computerized telecommunications device that allows customers of financial institutions to perform a variety of banking transactions without the assistance of a teller in a public location [12].

Table 11: Growth in No. of ATM Centers of State Bank of Hyderabad during 2017 -2022.

Year	No. of ATM Centers
2017 – 2018	2490
2018 – 2019	3300
2019 – 2020	3400
2020 – 2021	4000
2021 - 2022	5100

(Source: The annual reports of State Bank of Hyderabad)

Table 12: Growth in No. of ATM Centers of Andhra Bank during 2009-2022

Year	No. of ATM Centers
2017 – 2018	272
2018 – 2019	330
2019 – 2020	391
2020 – 2021	505
2021 - 2022	656

(Source: The annual reports of Andhra Bank)

VII. CONCLUSION

The proper stores of State Bank of Hyderabad have been the significant part to add up to stores and there is a nonstop development with respect to the decent store part in complete stores besides in 2009 and 2022. The percentage of State Bank of Hyderabad's total deposits comprised of saving deposits has decreased from 19.29 percent in 2013 to 18.78 percent in 2022. Current deposits have decreased from 20.55 percent in 2013 to 11.82 percent in 2022. This shows that proper store part has been expanded whereas current store part has been diminished in absolute stores. Throughout the study period, State Bank of Hyderabad's fixed deposits grew at a faster rate than the other components of total deposits—namely demand deposits and savings deposits. Andhra Bank's fixed deposits, which totaled Rs.7262 crores in 2013, have increased to Rs.32832 crores, but their proportion of total deposits has decreased to 66.43 percent in 2022 from 69.57 percent in 2013.

Throughout the course of the investigation, the amount of total advances granted by Andhra Bank has been steadily rising. Additionally, the bank's advances to its priority sector will increase to Rs. 12660 crores in 2022, up from Rs. 1874 crores in 2013. However, the percentage of total advances that went to advances in priority sectors decreased from 40.97 percent in 2013 to 36.97 percent in 2022. The State Bank of Hyderabad's deposit per office has increased by more than four times between 2013 and 2022, going from Rs.10.66 crores in 2013 to Rs.45.75 crores in 2022. The Andhra Bank's individual branch deposits during the same time office has been increased to more than three times. i.e. from Rs.10.63 crores in 2013 to Rs.3618 crores in 2022. The credit per branch office of the State Bank of Hyderabad has been increased by six times during 2013-2022. i.e., from Rs.0.54 in 2013 crores to Rs.3.27 crores in 2022, whereas the same of Andhra Bank during the same period increased by four and half times i.e., Rs.0.46 crores in 2013 to Rs.2.51 crores in 2022.

CONFLICTS OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest.

REFERENCES

- [1] Report on working of the monetary system (Chakravarthy Committee), 1985.
- [2] Report of the working group to review the system of cash credit (Chore Committee), 1991.
- [3] Reports on Trend & Progress Banking in India, RBI
- [4] Statistical Tables Relating to Banks in India, RBI.
- [5] Agarwal B.P., Commercial Banking in India, the Capital Publishing House, Delhi, 2022.
- [6] Amended, Profits and Profitability in Commercial Banks, Deep and Deep Publications, New Delhi, 2017.
- [7] Amanita. K.K., towards more Remunerative Development of Credit for Banking Profitability, Macmillan India Limited, New Delhi, 2020,
- [8] Bansal A.K., “Changing face of Indian Banking, Towards Safe and Sound Future”, Bank Economists Conference, 2022.
- [9] Base, A.K. Fundamentals of Banking and Theory and Practices, Fourth Editions, New Delhi.
- [10] Base C.R., Commercial Banking in the Planned Economy of India, Mittal Publications, New Delhi.
- [11] Report of Talwar Committee to review Customer Service in Banks 1978.
- [12] Report of the Banking Commission, 1972.
- [13] Report of the Committee on Customer Service in Banks (M.N. Goporia Committee) RBI, 2019.
- [14] Reports of the Currency & Finance, RBI
- [15] Report on productivity, efficiency and profitability in commercial banks (Luther Committee), 2020.
- [16] Biryani S.A.R. Growth of Public Sector Banks, Deep and Deep Publications, New Delhi.
- [17] Bharati Pathak., Indian Financial System, Pearson Education, New Delhi, 2021